

A short remark on Bong Han duct system (PVS) as a Neutrosophic bridge between Eastern and Western Medicine paradigms

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Abstract

In a previous paper in this journal (IJNS), it is mentioned about a possible approach of “*curemony*” as a middle way in order to reconcile Eastern and Western’s paradigms of medicine [1]. Although it is known in literature that there are some attempts to reconcile between Eastern and Western medicine paradigms, known as “*integrative medicine*,” here a new viewpoint is submitted, i.e. Bong Han *duct* system (PVS), which is a proof of Meridian system, can be a bridge between those two medicine paradigms in neutrosophic sense. This can be considered as a Neutrosophic Logic way to bridge or reconcile the age-old debates over the Western and Eastern approach to medicine. It is also hoped that there will be further research in this direction, especially to clarify the distinction between Pasteur’s *germ theory* and Bechamp’s *microzyma theory*. More research is obviously recommended. **Motivation of this paper:** to prove that Neutrosophic Logic offers a reconciliation towards better dialogue between Western and Eastern medicine systems. **Novelty aspect:** it is discussed here how Bong Han Duct system offers a proven and observable way to Meridian system, which in turn it can be a good start to begin meaningful dialogue between Western and Eastern systems.

Keywords: Pasteur, microzyma, Bechamp theory, meridian system, Bong Han Kim, Bong Han duct system, neutrosophic logic

1. Introduction

In the light of recent advancements on the use of Neutrosophic Logic in various branches of science and mathematics, this paper discuss possible application in medicine philosophy. See for instance [13-19].

This paper is inspired partly by the movie, *Jewel in the Palace* (Dae Jang Geum). One of these authors (VC) has a younger brother who likes to watch that movie. He already completed watching the entire series (more than 70 episodes) more than three times. According to a good documentary on that movie [11]:

A history book courageous woman is reawakened in a hit TV dramatization. In 1392, the Joseon Dynasty appeared. The rulers of Joseon would lead the Korean landmass until the administration fell, to be supplanted by a Japanese provincial system, in 1910. All things considered, Joseon's heritage suffers: It was one of the world's longest-running imperial administrations. In the "Joseon-Wangjo-Sillok" - "The Annals of the Joseon Dynasty," the official record of the realm - a lady named "Daejanggeum" is referenced. She lived during the rule of King Jungjong (1506~1544), and the archives disclose to us that she had been a low-positioning court woman who picked up the ruler's trust and was elevated to the most noteworthy positioned woman in the kitchen, and furthermore to regal doctor. In one notice in the archives, the ruler states, "I have nearly recuperated from the sickness of a couple of months. So I should offer honors to the individuals who put forth bunches of attempts to fix me. Give the imperial doctors and euinyeo (female associate) Daejanggeum blessings."

Figure 1. Jang Geum name was recorded in the "Joseon-Wangjo-Sillok" - "The Annals of the Joseon Dynasty." After Kang Min Su [11]

What is more interesting to these authors, is not only the depiction of royal palace at the time, but also the use of royal cuisine as medication, beside the use of acupuncture methods.[11]

Now it seems obvious for Western scholars to pause at this point and ask: "What? Acupuncture? Are you joking?"

This short review paper is discussing that approach: whether it is possible to reconcile both Eastern and Western medicine paradigms from the view point of Bong Han Kim's duct system (PVS) and its relation to Bechamp's microzyma.

As it is brought up in [1], it is notable by most medication experts, that Western way to deal with medication depends on "assaulting" an infection, individually. This is called *germ* hypothesis: one remedy for one ailment (Pasteur). On the contrary side, Eastern medication is situated specifically on old knowledge of *restoring* the parity (harmonious functions) of the body, at the end of the day: to blend our body and our live with nature. In spite of the fact that those two methodologies in medication and social insurance have caused such a large number of contentions and false impressions, really it is conceivable to do an exchange between them. From Neutrosophic Logic's point of view, a goal to the above clashing ideal models can be found in creating novel methodologies which acknowledge the two conventions in medication, or it is conceivable to call such a methodology: "*curemony*," for example by simultaneously relieving an infection and reestablishing harmony and returning concordance in one's body-mind-soul all in all.

Now it is known that one of the objections by Western scholars about the Eastern medicine (based on meridian points) is the unobservability of meridian vascular/duct system. This makes meridian system neglected in almost all textbooks taught in Western medicine schools. Therefore, here a new viewpoint is submitted, i.e. Bong Han *duct* system (PVS), which is a *proof of Meridian system*, can be a bridge between those two medicine paradigms in neutrosophic sense. This can be considered as a Neutrosophic Logic way to bridge or reconcile the age old debates over the Western and Eastern approach to medicine.

It would be a lot easier to merge both the eastern (ancient) and the modern western curative system in terms of neutrosophy. These neutrosophic intermediates will help further to boost dialogues between those Western and Eastern system and their useful information. This neutrosophic intermedicator is actually dealing with conscious of both non-matter and matter in terms of ancients and modern techniques.

2. Introduction to Bong Han duct system

Nonetheless, in literature it is recorded that Bong Han Kim is a Professor in Biology in Korea. Around 1950-1960 he found the vessel which is a "*duct*" to known Eastern Meridian system, which is already known in acupuncture medicine system. Therefore it seems like a bridge between Western and Eastern medicine paradigms. As it is mentioned in previous paper [1], this paper will discuss how those paradigms can be reconciled in Neutrosophic Logic, using a degree of Western medicine and a degree of Eastern medicine, as the neutral part of neutrosophy. To us, Bong Han duct system is a good way to start a healthy and meaningful dialogue between those two paradigms in medicine.

As Vitaly Vodanoy wrote, which can be rephrased as follows:

"In the 1960's Bong Han Kim found and described another vascular framework. He had the option to separate it unmistakably from vascular blood and lymph frameworks by the utilization of an assortment of techniques, which were accessible to him in the mid-twentieth century. He gave nitty gritty portrayal of the framework and made thorough graphs and photos in his distributions. He showed that this framework is made out of hubs and vessels, and it was answerable for tissue recovery. In any case, he didn't reveal in subtleties his

techniques. Thus, his outcomes are moderately dark from the vantage purpose of contemporary researchers. The stains that Kim utilized had been idealized and being used for over 100 years. In this manner, the names of the stains coordinated to the unequivocal conventions for the use with the specific cells or particles. Generally, it was not typically important to portray the strategy utilized except if it is altogether strayed from the first technique.”[9]

Although his method was almost forgotten until recently, it has been recovered again in the past decade. It is clear therefore, that Bonghan Kim’s work, who essentially (and without being aware of the work previously done by Bechamp) discovered that what we call the 'Meridian System' (known as the *Kyungrak System* in the Korean tongue) which exists in the body as an actual third anatomical vascular system, comprised of ducts, ductules, corpuscles, and a unique type of fluid, the contents of which tie directly back to Bechamp's own discoveries (work is still being done today on the mapping out of this anatomical system, as it is far more extensive than the old Oriental texts gave it credit.) See [4].

Remark on terminology:

“In a matter of seconds before the primary International Symposium on Primo Vascular System, which was held in Jecheon, Korea during September 17–18, 2010, Dr. Kwang-Sup Soh, recommended that it is critical to concur upon a solitary phrasing for the Bonghan framework. It was concurred that following terms would be embraced: Bong-Han System (BHS) - Primo Vascular System (PVS); Bonghan Duct (BHD)- Primo Vessel (PV); Bonghan Corpuscle (BHC)- Primo Node (PN); Bonghan Ductule - P-Subvessel; Bonghan Liquor-Primo Fluid (P-liquid); Sanalp-Microcell”[9].

Now in the next section, it will be discussed virus research, especially at their beginning.

Hidden the introduction of virology is a conviction that infections are monomorphism, they are fixed species, unchangeable; that each neurotic kind produces (typically) just a single explicit illness; that microforms never emerge endogenously, i.e., have supreme source with the host. Thus the worldview prompts conviction called "germ hypothesis" of Pasteur: for example one remedy for one disease.[6-7]

Bechamp recorded standard as the premise of another hypothesis about "infections." Briefly, this guideline holds that in every single living life form are organically indestructible anatomical components, which he called microzymas. They are freely living sorted out matures, equipped for creating compounds and fit for advancement into increasingly complex microforms, for example, microbes. Bechamp's proposition is that infection is a state of one's interior condition (landscape); that ailment (and its indications) are "conceived of us and in us"; and that malady isn't created by an assault of microentities yet considers forward their endogenous cause. [8]

All things considered, it is realized that Pasteur duplicated whatever he discovered Bechamp thoughts would fit in his own hypothesis. Consequently, Bechamp was unmistakably increasingly unique researcher contrasted with Pasteur.

3. A re-interpretation of diseases and virus from Bechamp's theory

This section begin by citing [4], which can be paraphrased as follows:

“Through a cautious perception of the wonders of the thickening of the blood just as the procedure of maturation; and as a methods for all the more accurately deciphering the basic idea of these marvels; Bechamp straightforwardly saw that there exist a layers of subcellular, miniaturized scale natural living structures known as 'microzymas', a word which when interpreted signifies 'minor ages'. These structures were alluded to without anyone else and by other people (who came later, and mentioned a similar objective facts) as some type of 'atomic granulations' (more on this beneath). These microzyma are littler in size than some other known types of small scale natural life, and fill in as the base establishment for the development of every other type of such life.”

Moreover, on a more recent setting, see Andrew Kaufmann's report on WHO's early investigation of the corona virus, before it was declared globally as an epidemic.¹

According to Dr. Andrew Kaufman's report, a “virus” as observed is actually an *exosome*. That is not impossible. Even if you want to be more assertive. It's not just the PCR test that is inaccurate. So the so-called virus is indeed questionable. Because it relates to the *germ theory* of Pasteur, meaning each disease will need one type of medicine [1][2].

That's not right. Pasteur's theory draws a lot from the real expert at the time: Bechamp.[4]

In essence, according to Bechamp, the source of the disease is most likely to be endogenous. Meaning from within the body when adjusting itself to the environment.

What is interesting to ask here is what kind of the changes in the environment that triggers the emergence of symptoms such as excessive thirs? Actually, it is known as one of the symptoms known for electromagnetic radiation. Therefore, it is no surprise that there are some allegations by experts: severe radiation disturbances arise in Wuhan and Italy and also the USA because of they are the locations where the massive 5G network has begun to be installed (see also Firstenberg's report [5]).

But this short paper is not intended to discuss more detailed about relation between 5G and covid-19, so this problem will be left to others to take up this matter and investigate further.

4. Concluding remarks

This paper continued our previous article, where possible approach of “*curemony*” is discussed as a middle Neutrosophic way in order to reconcile Eastern and Western's paradigms of medicine [1]. Although it is known in literature, that there are some attempts to reconcile between Eastern and Western medicine paradigms, known as

¹ Dr. Andrew Kaufman's interview on corona virus test. url: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f9mzdvoEjBc>

“integrative medicine,” here it is submitted a viewpoint that Bong Han duct system (PVS) which is a proof of meridian system, can be a neutrosophic bridge between those two medicine paradigms.

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As mentioned in our previous paper [1], it is also discussed how those paradigms can be reconciled in Neutrosophic Logic. To us, Bong Han duct system (PVS) is a good way to start a healthy and meaningful dialogue between those two paradigms in medicine.

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